

Titanium Substitution Facilitating Oxygen and Manganese Redox in Sodium Layered Oxide Cathode

Junhua Zhou, Huimin Hu, Jiaqi Wang, Qitao Shi, Xueyu Lian, Lijun Liu, Alicja Bachmatiuk, Jingyu Sun, Ruizhi Yang, Jin-Ho Choi,* and Mark H. Rummeli*

Sodium layered oxide with anion redox activity (SLO-A) stands out as a promising cathode material for sodium-ion batteries due to its impressive capacity and high voltage resulting from Mn- and O-redox processes. However, the SLO-A faces significant challenges in cycling stability and rate performance, primarily due to the poor reversibility and sluggish kinetics of the O-redox. In this study, a novel Ti-doped material, $\text{Na}_{2/3}\text{Li}_{2/9}\text{Mn}_{53/72}\text{Ti}_{1/24}\text{O}_2$ (NLMT0), exhibiting remarkable characteristics such as a notable rate capacity (130 mAh g^{-1} at 3C, where 1C equals 200 mA g^{-1}) and excellent cycling retention (85.4% after 100 cycles at 0.5C) is introduced. Employing electrochemical differential analyses, the contributions to the superior performance arising from the Mn- and O-redox processes are quantitatively delineated. The optimized performance of NLMT0 is attributed, in part, to the enhanced stability of both bulk and interface structures. The introduction of Ti through substitution not only contributes to this stability but also allows for the fine-tuning of the material's electron configurations. This is achieved by augmenting the density of states near the Fermi energy level, as well as elevating the O 2p and Mn 3d orbits. This research advances sodium-ion battery technology.

1. Introduction

Sodium-ion battery (SIB) is one of the most promising next-generation battery technologies, particularly for large-scale energy storage grids, owing to the cost-effectiveness and abundance of its raw materials, such as current collectors, electrolytes, and electrodes.^[1-3] However, the energy density of SIBs is much worse compared to lithium-ion batteries, mainly due to the relatively lower capacity and voltage of conventional cathodes (e.g., layered oxides, polyanionic compounds, Prussian blue analogs, and organic materials).^[4,5]

A new type of cathode material, sodium layered oxide with additional anion redox activity (SLO-A), has been frequently reported, because of its large specific capacity ($>150 \text{ mAh g}^{-1}$) and high average voltage ($>3.8 \text{ V}$) in SIBs. The extra oxygen redox in SLO-A

J. Zhou, H. Hu, J. Wang, Q. Shi, X. Lian, J. Sun, R. Yang, J.-H. Choi, M. H. Rummeli
College of Energy
Soochow Institute for Energy and Materials InnovationS (SIEMIS)
Key Laboratory of Advanced Carbon Materials and Wearable Energy Technologies of Jiangsu Province
Soochow University
Suzhou 215006, P. R. China
E-mail: jhchoi@suda.edu.cn; mhr1@suda.edu.cn

J. Zhou, H. Hu, J. Wang, Q. Shi, X. Lian, J. Sun, R. Yang, J.-H. Choi, M. H. Rummeli
Jiangsu Key Laboratory of Advanced Negative Carbon Technologies
Soochow University
Suzhou, Jiangsu 215123, P. R. China

L. Liu
School of Energy and Power Engineering
Xi'an Jiaotong University
No. 28, Xianning West Road, Xi'an, Shaanxi 710049, China
A. Bachmatiuk
LUKASIEWICZ Research Network
PORT Polish Center for Technology Development
Stablowicka 147, Wroclaw 54-066, Poland

M. H. Rummeli
Institute for Complex Materials
IFW Dresden
20 Helmholtz Strasse, 01069 Dresden, Germany
M. H. Rummeli
Centre of Polymer and Carbon Materials
Polish Academy of Sciences
M. Curie-Skłodowskiej 34, Zabrze 41-819, Poland
M. H. Rummeli
VSB-Technical University of Ostrava
Centre for Energy and Environmental Technologies
Institute of Environmental Technology
17. listopadu 15, Ostrava 70800, Czech Republic

 The ORCID identification number(s) for the author(s) of this article can be found under <https://doi.org/10.1002/admi.202400190>

© 2024 The Authors. Advanced Materials Interfaces published by Wiley-VCH GmbH. This is an open access article under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/) License, which permits use, distribution and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

DOI: 10.1002/admi.202400190

originates from the special O 2p non-bonding band,^[6,7] which can be activated by elements without 3d electrons (e.g., Li⁺, 1s²; Mg²⁺, 1s²2s²),^[8–13] elements with ten 3d electrons (e.g., Zn²⁺, [Ar]3d¹⁰),^[14,15] or vacancies at transition metal (TM) sites.^[16–18] However, the poor reversibility and sluggish kinetics of anion redox also lead to the inferior cycling stability and rate capacity of the SLO-A.^[19,20]

Element doping, such as using Ti,^[21–23] Cu,^[24] and Fe,^[25] is one of the most popular strategies to tackle the challenges toward oxygen redox, since the elements can adjust both the crystal structure and electron configuration of the SLO-A. For example, the Ti doping could reduce the ordering of Mg and Mn in the TM layer, and tune the electron configuration, which greatly enhances the electrochemical property of the Na_{2/3}Mg_{1/3}Ti_{1/6}Mn_{1/2}O₂ cathode.^[23] However, the exploration of the functions of doping elements is rare, from a comprehensive point of view, including the bulk structure, electron configuration, interphase stability, and kinetics. Moreover, there is no work, which can elucidate how much the doping element facilitates the charge compensation of cation and anion redox quantitatively, to the best of our knowledge.

Herein, we select the most popular doping element, Ti, as a model, to explore its multi-functions in SLO-A. 1) The Ti can improve the stability of bulk structure, and avoid the formation of cracks. 2) The sustainable bulk structure will enhance the stability of solid electrolyte interphase (SEI) by limiting electrolyte permeating along the cracks. 3) The boosted density of states (DOS) near the Fermi energy (E_F) level leads to increased conductivity and accelerated dynamics. 4) The elevated O 2p and Mn 3d orbitals can facilitate the O-redox and Mn-redox respectively. As a result, the Ti-doped material exhibits excellent cycling stability with an ultralow capacity decay per cycle of 0.146% during 100 cycles at 0.5C. The enhanced performance from contributions of the O- and Mn-redox was also proved by a quantitative differential electrochemical analysis.

2. Results and Discussion

2.1. Preparation and Structure

Na_{2/3}Li_{2/9}Mn_{7/9}O₂ (NLMO) was synthesized by a facile solid-state reaction at an annealing temperature of 800 °C for 20 h in air. Typically, the Ti³⁺/Ti⁴⁺ redox couple in layered oxides located at a potential less than 1.5 V (vs Na/Na⁺), such as O3-NaTiO₂,^[26] P2-Na_{0.66}Li_{0.22}Ti_{0.78}O₂,^[27] and O3-Na_{0.73}Li_{0.26}Ti_{0.73}O₂.^[28] Accordingly, the doping amount of non-active Ti in the cathode should be minimized, and 1/24 was selected in this work (Na_{2/3}Li_{2/9}Mn_{53/72}Ti_{1/24}O₂, NLMTO).

Both the NLMO and NLMTO, with high purity, can be assigned to the *P63/mmc* space group (XRD results, **Figure 1a,b**; Tables **S1** and **S2**, Supporting Information). More specifically, they belong to the P2 structure, where the “2” represents the repeat stacking sequence of O atoms (ABBA, **Figure 1c**), and the “P” denotes the trigonal prismatic coordination environment of Na in oxygen polyhedron (**Figure 1d**).^[29] In the TM layer, partial Mn atoms are orderly substituted by Li (the NLMO), or Li and Ti (the NLMTO), which generates the superstructure (**Figure 1e**), proved by extra diffraction peaks at 17–30° (**Figure 1a,b**). Moreover, the most prominent (002) peak at ≈15.9° (**Figure 1a,b**), which relates to highly oriented layer structures, is demonstrated by high-angle

annular dark-field scanning transmission electron microscopy (HAADF-STEM) images (**Figure S1**, Supporting Information).

The hexagonal crystal structure determines the hexagonal morphology of the NLMO and NLMTO, with particle size of about 1.5 μm (SEM images, **Figure S2**, Supporting Information). The tiny Ti substitution does not influence the structure and morphology of the material, which originates from the similar ionic radii of Ti and Mn atoms (Mn⁴⁺, 53 pm; Ti⁴⁺, 60.5 pm).^[30] Even so, the existence of Ti in NLMTO can be proved by EDS mapping and XPS results (**Figure 1f–h**; **Figures S3** and **S4**, Supporting Information).

2.2. Structure Evolution and Charge Compensation Mechanism

In situ XRD patterns were synchronously collected during the 1st charge–discharge process at 0.1C (1C = 200 mA g⁻¹) between 1.5 and 4.5 V (**Figure 2a,b**; **Figure S5**, Supporting Information). Upon charging, the (002) peak gradually shifts to the low diffraction angle direction (**Figure 2a,b**), which indicates an enlarged layer distance along the *c*-axis. This mainly originates from the enhanced repulsive interaction between the adjacent oxygen stacking layer during the deintercalation of Na⁺ process.^[23] Meanwhile, the peak intensity gradually decreases (**Figure 2a,b**), owing to the generated stacking faults.^[13] More importantly, a new peak appears in the NLMO at ≈16.8° (**Figure 2a**, marked with dash lines) at a low state of charge, which is assigned to the OP4 phase,^[22] the mixture of P2 phase (≈15.8°) and O2 phase (≈18°), demonstrating the slipping of transition metal stacking layer upon deep Na⁺ deintercalation. In contrast, such phase transition is not observed in the NLMTO, which implies that Ti doping can boost the structural stability. A basically reversible variation can be observed during discharging for the NLMO and NLMTO.

Moreover, after 7 days of water erosion, the NLMTO shows a much stronger (002) peak compared to the NLMO (**Figure S6**, Supporting Information). This demonstrates the Ti substitution can also improve the air stability of the NLMTO, which is crucial, especially for hygroscopic sodium cathode materials. From ex situ Raman spectra (**Figure S7**, Supporting Information), the NLMTO exhibits much stronger peak intensity when being charged to 4.5 V than the NLMO, which again proves its better structural sustainability.

Materials at pristine state, after initially being charged to 4.5 V, and then discharged back to 1.5 V (**Figure 3a**), were collected to explore the charge compensation mechanism by ex situ XPS. Owing to the various sources of oxygen species in batteries, such as from impurities, SEI layers, and bulk materials, the effectiveness of applying the surface-sensitive XPS technique to analyze the O-redox mechanism needs to be clarified first.^[20,31] 1) The ex situ XPS samples were collected in the 1st cycle, where the SEI layer began to generate, and thus the O signal from SEI should be tiny; 2) The O peaks from the lattice oxygen (<532 eV) and SEI layer (>532 eV) are located at disparate binding energy, and can be decoupled easily.

At the pristine state (**Figure 3b,c**, the top panels), in addition to peaks from impurities, the remaining peak at ≈529.5 eV can be assigned to the O²⁻ from bulk materials. When materials were charged to 4.5 V (**Figure 3b,c**, the middle panels), a new peak

Figure 1. Structure and composition of the NLMO and NLMTO. a,b) Rietveld refinement of XRD patterns. Extra peaks at 17–30° represent the existence of superstructure. c–e) Structure models. The prismatic Na coordination in d) and ABBA repeat stacking sequence of O in c) indicate the P2 structure. The models in e) show the special Li–Mn and Li–Mn–Ti superstructures. f–g) EDS mapping images (Scale bar, 50 nm). h) Ti 2p XPS spectra.

at higher binding energy (≈ 530.8 eV) appeared, which demonstrates the lattice oxygen is oxidized (O^{n-} , $0 < n < 2$). After electrodes were finally discharged back to 1.5 V (Figure 3b,c, the bottom panels), the peak from O^{2-} intensifies, but that from O^{n-} weakens, which reveals a partial reduction of the lattice oxygen. Although the mechanism is identical, the NLMTO shows obviously higher O-redox reversibility than the NLMO (Figure 3d).

As for the cationic redox (Mn-redox, Figure 3e; Figure S8, Supporting Information), the Mn element retains its chemical valence during charging process (invariable binding energy, ≈ 642 eV), owing to the highest oxidation state of Mn (Mn^{4+}) in the pristine materials. During discharging (Figure 3e; Figure S8, Supporting Information), the peak shifts to lower binding energy (≈ 641 eV), which proves the Mn^{4+} can be reduced and contribute capacity. Overall, in the 1st cycle, only the O is oxidized during charging, and both the O and Mn are reduced upon the following discharging (Figure 3a).

2.3. Electrochemical Performance and Kinetics

Coin cells were assembled, with carbonate electrolytes (1 M $NaPF_6$ in EC: DMC = 1:1 vol% with 5% FEC), to evaluate the electrochemical performance and kinetics of the NLMO and NLMTO. During the 1st charging process, the NLMTO exhibits only one long platform at 4.25 V (Figure 4a) and a corresponding strong peak (V vs dQ/dV curves, Figure 4b), assigned to the O oxidation. Upon the following 2nd charging, an extra slope (Figure 4a) and a small peak (Figure 4b) appear at a potential below 3.8 V, indexed to the Mn oxidation.

The NLMO shows similar charge–discharge curves (Figure S9, Supporting Information), but obviously lower capacity than the NLMTO at 0.1C (NLMO: 200 mAh g^{-1} , NLMTO: 230 mAh g^{-1}). To assess how the Ti substitution facilitates the O and Mn redox quantitatively, another kind of differential curve, Q versus dV/dQ (Figure 4c; Figures S10 and S11, Supporting

Figure 2. Structure evolution of the NLMO and NLMTO. a, b) Charge–discharge curves in the 1st cycle and corresponding in situ XRD patterns.

Information), was introduced. The valley in Q versus dV/dQ curves (Figure 4c), correspond to the platform in charge–discharge curves (Figure 4a), and also relate to the peak in V versus dQ/dV patterns (Figure 4b).^[32] Both the facilitated O and Mn redox contribute to the increased capacity of the NLMTO (contribution ratio: O-redox, 54.1%; Mn-redox, 45.9%; Figure S12, Supporting Information).

The Ti doping is also effective when batteries operate at higher current density. Despite capacities decrease with increased C-rates from 0.2C to 3C, the NLMTO shows higher capacity than the NLMO invariably (e.g., NLMO: 74 mAh g⁻¹, NLMTO: 126 mAh g⁻¹, at 3C, Figure 4d). More specifically, the capacity decade at higher C rates mainly originates from the O-redox (contribution ratio: O-redox, 69.5%; Mn-redox, 30.5%; Figure S13, Supporting Information), which reveals the sluggish kinetics of lattice oxygen.

The moderate current density (0.5C) was selected to further evaluate long cycling performances (Figure 4e). The NLMTO displays much higher capacity retention than the NLMO after 100 cycles (NLMO: 46.2%, NLMTO: 85.4%, Figure 4e). The enhanced stability originates from both the facilitated Mn-redox (NLMO, 48.2%; NLMTO, 89.7%; Figure 4f; Figure S14, Supporting Information) and O-redox (NLMO, 41.8%; NLMTO, 73.7%; Figure 4g; Figure S14, Supporting Information). Besides kinetics, the stability of O-redox is also worse than that of Mn-redox. Actually, the ultralow capacity decay per cycle of

the NLMTO (0.146%) is superior to that of most SLO-A cathodes, such as Na_{0.6}Li_{0.2}Mn_{0.8}O₂,^[8] Na_{0.66}Li_{0.18}Fe_{0.12}Mn_{0.7}O₂,^[25] Na_{2/3}Mg_{1/3}Mn_{2/3}O₂,^[10] Na_{2/3}Mg_{1/3}Ti_{1/6}Mn_{1/2}O₂,^[23] Na_{2/3}Zn_{2/9}Mn_{7/9}O₂,^[14] and Na_{4/7}Mn_{6/7}O₂ (Table S3, Supporting Information).^[16]

The Ti doping also accelerates the kinetics of the materials. Despite the similar resistance from SEI (R_{SEI}), the NLMTO shows much lower charge transfer impedance than the NLMO (R_{CT} ; NLMO, 1625 Ω ; NLMTO, 628 Ω ; Figure 4h; Figure S15, Supporting Information). Moreover, the diffusion coefficient of Na⁺ in the NLMTO during the O- and Mn-redox process increases simultaneously, driven from the galvanostatic intermittent titration technique (GITT) results (Figure S16, Supporting Information).

2.4. Bulk and Interphase Stability

To elucidate why the modified material shows greatly enhanced cycling stability, failure analysis was conducted by using cycled electrodes. The NLMO exhibits an obviously lower (002) diffraction angle compared to the NLMTO (NLMO, $\approx 15.8^\circ$; NLMTO, $\approx 16^\circ$, Figure 5a; Figure S17, Supporting Information), which reveals its expanded layer distance along the c -axis. This will further induce the formation of large cracks at the edge of the NLMO particle, shown in the HADDF-STEM images (Figure 5b). In

Figure 3. Charge compensation of the NLMO and NLMTO. a) The initial charge–discharge curves. Three labeled states (Pristine, 4.5 and 1.5 V) were selected to test ex situ XPS. The charge compensation mechanism is also summarized in (a). b,c) Ex situ XPS O 1s spectra. d) The mole ratio of oxidized O^{2-} (O^{n-}) among the total oxygen signals. e) Ex situ XPS Mn $2p_{3/2}$ spectra.

contrast, with the Ti substitution, the NLMTO displays less local structure distortion during the repetitive Na^+ (de)intercalation (Figure 5b).

The bulk structure evolution also induces interphase instability. Specifically, the electrolyte will permeate along the cracks, and be oxidized to form SEI layer on the newly exposed electrode surface. As a result, the NLMO shows much thicker and more uneven SEI layers than the NLMTO (NLMO, ≈ 13 nm; NLMTO, ≈ 6 nm; Figure 5c,d; Figure S18, Supporting Information). Meanwhile, more amounts of SEI species were generated on the NLMO compared to the NLMTO, including organic compounds (e.g., C-O, O 1s XPS, Figure 5e) and inorganic compounds (e.g., NaF, F 1s XPS, Figure 5f). Overall, the enhanced bulk and interphase sustainability jointly contribute to the desirable cycling performance of the NLMTO.

2.5. DFT Calculations

The first-principles density functional theory (DFT) calculations were finally performed to elucidate the enhanced capacity and dynamics of the NLMTO. The total DOS shows that the intro-

duction of Ti increases DOS near the E_F level (Figure 6a, the top panel), which indicates an improvement in the conductivity and kinetics of the NLMTO. Notably, the presence of the low-lying Ti 3d orbital in the NLMTO supports the low redox potential of Ti^{4+} (Figure S19, Supporting Information). Furthermore, the electrons involved in the Ti–O bonding are primarily localized around the oxygen ions, which contributes to boosting the O 2p orbital (Figure 6a, the middle panel; Figure 6b). These electrons engaged in Ti–O bonding also participate in Mn–O bonding, due to the low amount of Ti in the NLMTO. This leads to the orbital hybridization, and the elevated Mn 3d orbital (Figure 6a, the bottom panel; Figure 6b). The heightened O 2p and Mn 3d energy levels of the NLMTO facilitate the O-redox and Mn-redox respectively, and therefore promote the capacity utilization. Moreover, the higher energy level of O^{2-} 2p compared with the Mn^{4+} 3d t_{2g} proves the existence of O-redox.

3. Conclusion

In summary, we have successfully designed a novel Ti-doped material that demonstrates exceptional electrochemical performance, including a high specific capacity (220 mAh g^{-1} at 0.1C),

Figure 4. Electrochemical behaviors of the NLMO and NLMTO. a–c) The charge curves at 0.1C (1C = 200 mA g⁻¹), corresponding V versus dQ/dV patterns, and Q versus dV/dQ patterns. The labeled Mn-redox and O-redox in (b) and (c) are used to calculate their capacity contribution. d,e) Rate capacity and cycling performance at 0.5C. f,g) The calculated capacity of Mn-redox and O-redox driven from differential curves. h) Resistance from the SEI layer (R_{SEI}) and charge transfer (R_{CT}).

remarkable rate capability (130 mAh g⁻¹ at 3C), and outstanding cycling stability (maintaining 85.4% capacity after 100 cycles at 0.5C). Utilizing quantitative electrochemical differential methods, such as V versus dQ/dV and Q versus dV/dQ, we have conclusively established that the enhanced performance of the Na_{2/3}Li_{2/9}Mn_{53/72}Ti_{1/24}O₂ (NLMTO) cathode can be attributed to synergistic contributions from both Mn-redox and O-redox processes. The optimization of performance arises, in part, from the bolstered stability of both bulk and interface structures within the NLMTO. The introduction of Ti through substitution plays a crucial role in this enhancement, as it not only contributes to improved stability but also elevates the density of states (DOS) near the Fermi energy level (E_F). This increase in DOS results in enhanced conductivity and accelerated dynamics of the NLMTO, positively impacting its overall electrochemical performance. Additionally, the heightened O 2p and Mn 3d orbitals further facilitate the O-redox and Mn-redox processes, respectively, thereby improving capacity utilization. Finally, our study not only validates the superior performance of the NLMTO cathode but also elucidates the underlying mechanisms behind its enhanced electrochemical properties. This research contributes valuable insights

for the design and development of advanced cathode materials with improved stability, conductivity, and overall performance in sodium-ion battery applications.

4. Experimental Section

Material Preparation: Na_{2/3}Li_{2/9}Mn_{53/72}Ti_{1/24}O₂ (NLMTO) was prepared by a typical solid-state reaction. First, Na₂CO₃ (Aladdin, 99.99%), Li₂CO₃ (Aladdin, 99.99%), TiO₂ (Aladdin, 99.99%) and MnO₂ (Aladdin, 99.95%) of stoichiometric ratio with an excess of 2 mol% Li₂CO₃ and Na₂CO₃ were milled altogether using a high energy ball mill machine (Ants scientific instruments CO., LTD) for 2 h at the speed of 500 rpm. After that, the mixture was pelleted, and calcined in a tube furnace at 800 °C in air for 20 h. Na_{2/3}Li_{2/9}Mn_{7/9}O₂ (NLMO) was prepared at the same condition without TiO₂.

Electrode Preparation and Battery Assembly: A slurry was prepared by mixing NLMO or NLMTO active materials, Super P (SP, TIMCAL) conductive additives, and PVDF (Arkema, HSV900) binders with a mass ratio of 70: 20: 10 in NMP (Aladdin, 99.9%) under magnetic stirring for 2 h. The obtained slurry was then cast on Al current collectors using a scraper and dried at 80 °C for 2 h. The electrodes were then cut into discs (diameter of 14 mm) with loading of ≈2 mg cm⁻² (thickness of ≈50 μm), which were

Figure 5. Bulk and interphase structures of the NLMO and NLMTO after cycling. a) XRD patterns. b) STEM images. c,d) TEM images. e, f) O 1s and F 1s XPS spectra. The XPS signals are composed of species from both the bulk structure and SEI layer.

further dried at 120 °C for 6 h in a vacuum oven. 2032-type coin cells were assembled in a glove box ($O_2 < 0.1$ ppm, $H_2O < 0.1$ ppm) with the prepared cathode, sodium metal anode (thickness of ≈ 400 μm , Alfa Aesar), carbonate electrolyte (1 M NaPF₆ in EC: DMC = 1:1 vol% with 5% FEC, DoDoChem), and glass fiber separator (Whatman).

Electrochemical Measurements: Charge–discharge tests (1C = 200 mA g⁻¹, 1.5–4.5 V) were conducted at 25 °C using a CT3001A system (Wuhan LAND). GITT was performed with a pulse current of 0.1C for 30 min with a 5 h interruption between each pulse. EIS was performed between 1000000 and 0.01 Hz with a bias voltage of 0.005 V using a CHI800D system (CH Instruments).

Physical Measurements: All XRD patterns obtained in this research were recorded using a Bruker D8 Advance diffractometer with a Cu $K\alpha$ radiation source operating at 40 kV and 40 mA. The XRD patterns were

refined using the Rietveld method and GSAS software. For in situ XRD tests, a stainless-steel Swagelok-type battery with a Be window was assembled and tested at 0.1C between 1.5 and 4.5 V, with recording more than 100 XRD scans synchronously. The Raman spectra were measured through a micro-Raman spectrometer (Horiba Jobin Yvon, HR Evolution) using a neon laser with a wavelength of 532 nm. SEM images were obtained using a Hitachi SU8010 SEM operating at 10 kV and 10 mA. XPS samples were tested using a vacuum transfer chamber to avoid contact with air. XPS patterns were obtained using a Thermo Fisher Escalab 250Xi XPS instrument with Al $K\alpha$ radiation source. Binding energy in this work was calibrated based on carbon contamination using the C 1s peak at 284.4 eV. TEM, HADDF-STEM, and TEM-EDS mapping images were captured using a spherical aberration-corrected FEI Titan Themis Cubed G2 300 TEM operating at 80 kV.

Figure 6. DFT calculations of the NLMO and NLMTO. a) The total, O 2p, and Mn 3d density of states (DOS). The Fermi energy (E_F) level is set to be 0 eV. b) Schematic illustration of the energy levels. The red, blue, and orange arrow lines represent the locations of the top Mn^{4+} 3d t_{2g} , O^{2-} 2p, and the bottom Mn^{4+} 3d e_g orbitals respectively.

DFT Calculations: First-principles DFT calculations were performed using the projector-augmented wave (PAW) method^[33] and the Perdew–Burke–Ernzerhof (PBE) exchange–correlation function^[34] in the Vienna Ab-initio Simulation Package.^[35,36] The plane-wave with a cutoff energy of 500 eV was adopted in all calculations. During structural optimization, all atoms were allowed to relax until the force exerted on each atom was less than 0.02 eV Å⁻¹. Meanwhile, the effects of spin-polarized and long-range van der Waals interactions were also considered in our calculations. Here, Hubbard U potential to describe the Coulomb electron interaction precisely was employed. The DFT + U method was used to treat the localized 3d electrons of Mn. According to the previous works, we set the U value of 4.8 and J value of 0.8 for Mn.^[37]

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

Acknowledgements

MHR thanks the National Natural Science Foundation of China (Grant Nos. 52071225 and 51672181), the Department of Human Resources and Social Security of Jiangsu Province (100 Talents Project), the Czech Republic, Institute of Environmental Technology. This article was produced with the financial support of the European Union under the REFRESH – Research Excellence For REgion Sustainability and High-tech Industries project number CZ.10.03.01/00/22_003/0000048 via the Operational Programme Just Transition. This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation program under the grant agreement No. 101087143. Junhua Zhou, Huimin Hu, and Jiaqi Wang contributed equally to this work.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Keywords

anion redox, bulk structure, electron configuration, electrochemical differential analysis, sodium layered oxide, Ti substitution

Received: February 28, 2024
Published online: April 9, 2024

- [1] C. Vaalma, D. Buchholz, M. Weil, S. Passerini, *Nat. Rev. Mater.* **2018**, *3*, 18013.
- [2] J. W. Choi, D. Aurbach, *Nat. Rev. Mater.* **2016**, *1*, 16013.
- [3] D. Larcher, J. M. Tarascon, *Nat. Chem.* **2015**, *7*, 19.
- [4] R. Usiskin, Y. Lu, J. Popovic, M. Law, P. Balaya, Y.-S. Hu, J. Maier, *Nat. Rev. Mater.* **2021**, *6*, 1020.
- [5] N. Yabuuchi, K. Kubota, M. Dahbi, S. Komaba, *Chem. Rev.* **2014**, *114*, 11636.
- [6] D. H. Seo, J. Lee, A. Urban, R. Malik, S. Kang, G. Ceder, *Nat. Chem.* **2016**, *8*, 692.

- [7] G. Assat, J.-M. Tarascon, *Nat. Energy* **2018**, *3*, 373.
- [8] X. Rong, J. Liu, E. Hu, Y. Liu, Y. Wang, J. Wu, X. Yu, K. Page, Y.-S. Hu, W. Yang, H. Li, X.-Q. Yang, L. Chen, X. Huang, *Joule* **2018**, *2*, 125.
- [9] X. Rong, E. Hu, Y. Lu, F. Meng, C. Zhao, X. Wang, Q. Zhang, X. Yu, L. Gu, Y.-S. Hu, H. Li, X. Huang, X.-Q. Yang, C. Delmas, L. Chen, *Joule* **2019**, *3*, 503.
- [10] K. Dai, J. Wu, Z. Zhuo, Q. Li, S. Sallis, J. Mao, G. Ai, C. Sun, Z. Li, W. E. Gent, W. C. Chueh, Y.-d. Chuang, R. Zeng, Z.-x. Shen, F. Pan, S. Yan, L. F. J. Piper, Z. Hussain, G. Liu, W. Yang, *Joule* **2019**, *3*, 518.
- [11] U. Maitra, R. A. House, J. W. Somerville, N. Tapia-Ruiz, J. G. Lozano, N. Guerrini, R. Hao, K. Luo, L. Jin, M. A. Perez-Osorio, F. Massel, D. M. Pickup, S. Ramos, X. Lu, D. E. McNally, A. V. Chadwick, F. Giustino, T. Schmitt, L. C. Duda, M. R. Roberts, P. G. Bruce, *Nat. Chem.* **2018**, *10*, 288.
- [12] Q. Wang, S. Mariyappan, G. Rousse, A. V. Morozov, B. Porcheron, R. Dedryvere, J. Wu, W. Yang, L. Zhang, M. Chakir, M. Avdeev, M. Deschamps, Y. S. Yu, J. Cabana, M. L. Doublet, A. M. Abakumov, J. M. Tarascon, *Nat. Mater.* **2021**, *20*, 353.
- [13] R. A. House, U. Maitra, M. A. Perez-Osorio, J. G. Lozano, L. Jin, J. W. Somerville, L. C. Duda, A. Nag, A. Walters, K. J. Zhou, M. R. Roberts, P. G. Bruce, *Nature* **2020**, *577*, 502.
- [14] X. Bai, M. Sathiy, B. Mendoza-Sánchez, A. Iadecola, J. Vergnet, R. Dedryvere, M. Saubanère, A. M. Abakumov, P. Rozier, J. M. Tarascon, *Adv. Energy Mater.* **2018**, *8*, 1802379.
- [15] Y. Wang, L. Wang, H. Zhu, J. Chu, Y. Fang, L. Wu, L. Huang, Y. Ren, C. J. Sun, Q. Liu, X. Ai, H. Yang, Y. Cao, *Adv. Funct. Mater.* **2020**, *30*, 1910327.
- [16] B. Mortemard de Boisse, S. i. Nishimura, E. Watanabe, L. Lander, A. Tsuchimoto, J. Kikkawa, E. Kobayashi, D. Asakura, M. Okubo, A. Yamada, *Adv. Energy Mater.* **2018**, *8*, 1800409.
- [17] C. Zhao, Q. Wang, Y. Lu, L. Jiang, L. Liu, X. Yu, L. Chen, B. Li, Y.-S. Hu, *Energy Stor. Mater.* **2019**, *20*, 395.
- [18] M. Ben Yahia, J. Vergnet, M. Saubanere, M. L. Doublet, *Nat. Mater.* **2019**, *18*, 496.
- [19] G. Assat, C. Delacourt, D. A. D. Corte, J.-M. Tarascon, *J. Electrochem. Soc.* **2016**, *163*, A2965.
- [20] G. Assat, D. Foix, C. Delacourt, A. Iadecola, R. Dedryvere, J. M. Tarascon, *Nat. Commun.* **2017**, *8*, 2219.
- [21] H. Xu, C. Cheng, S. Chu, X. Zhang, J. Wu, L. Zhang, S. Guo, H. Zhou, *Adv. Funct. Mater.* **2020**, *30*, 2005164.
- [22] X. Cao, X. Li, Y. Qiao, M. Jia, F. Qiu, Y. He, P. He, H. Zhou, *ACS Energy Lett.* **2019**, *4*, 2409.
- [23] C. Zhao, Z. Yao, J. Wang, Y. Lu, X. Bai, A. Aspuru-Guzik, L. Chen, Y.-S. Hu, *Chem* **2019**, *5*, 2913.
- [24] P.-F. Wang, Y. Xiao, N. Piao, Q.-C. Wang, X. Ji, T. Jin, Y.-J. Guo, S. Liu, T. Deng, C. Cui, L. Chen, Y.-G. Guo, X.-Q. Yang, C. Wang, *Nano Energy* **2020**, *69*, 104474.
- [25] L. Yang, X. Li, J. Liu, S. Xiong, X. Ma, P. Liu, J. Bai, W. Xu, Y. Tang, Y. Y. Hu, M. Liu, H. Chen, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2019**, *141*, 6680.
- [26] D. Wu, X. Li, B. Xu, N. Twu, L. Liu, G. Ceder, *Energy Environ. Sci.* **2015**, *8*, 195.
- [27] Y. Wang, X. Yu, S. Xu, J. Bai, R. Xiao, Y. S. Hu, H. Li, X. Q. Yang, L. Chen, X. Huang, *Nat. Commun.* **2013**, *4*, 2365.
- [28] Y. Cao, Q. Zhang, Y. Wei, Y. Guo, Z. Zhang, W. Huang, K. Yang, W. Chen, T. Zhai, H. Li, Y. Cui, *Adv. Funct. Mater.* **2019**, *30*, 1907023.
- [29] C. Zhao, Q. Wang, Zhenpeng Yao, J. W. B. Sánchez-Lengeling, F. Ding, X. Qi, Y. Lu, X. Bai, BaohuaLi, HLi, A. Aspuru-Guzik, X. Huang, C. Delmas, M. Wagemaker, L. Chen, Y.-S. Hu, *Science* **2020**, *370*, 708.
- [30] M. Rahm, R. Hoffmann, N. W. Ashcroft, *Chem. - Eur. J.* **2016**, *22*, 14625.

- [31] J. Zhou, Z. Chen, G. Yu, K. Ma, X. Lian, S. Li, Q. Shi, J. Wang, L. Guo, Y. Liu, A. Bachmatiuk, J. Sun, R. Yang, J. H. Choi, M. H. Rummeli, *Small Methods* **2022**, *6*, 2200449.
- [32] J. Zhou, X. Lian, Y. You, Q. Shi, Y. Liu, X. Yang, L. Liu, D. Wang, J. H. Choi, J. Sun, R. Yang, M. H. Rummeli, *Adv. Funct. Mater.* **2021**, *31*, 2102047.
- [33] P. E. Blochl, *Phys Rev B Condens Matter* **1994**, *50*, 17953.
- [34] J. P. Perdew, K. Burke, M. Ernzerhof, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **1996**, *77*, 3865.
- [35] G. Kresse, J. Furthmüller, *Phys. Rev. B* **1996**, *54*, 11169.
- [36] G. Kresse, D. Joubert, *Phys. Rev. B* **1999**, *59*, 1758.
- [37] L. Li, L. Zhu, L.-H. Xu, T.-M. Cheng, W. Wang, X. Li, Q.-T. Sui, *J. Mater. Chem. A* **2014**, *2*, 4251.